

Insect resistance

Screening for leaffolder resistance

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Thirty-one rice varieties were screened in fields at Pattambi for leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée resistance.

Varieties received through international collaborative projects were planted in 5-m rows at 25 × 25 cm spacing.

Susceptible variety Jaya was planted in border rows. Susceptible check was TN1. Periodic observations started when TN1 plants showed 40% attacked leaves. When the test varieties were scored, TN1 had 68.8% attacked leaves. Resistance rating by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice was based on the corrected percentage of damage.

GEB24 and PTB33 were highly resistant. TKM6, IR21937-26-2-3, Sri Lankan varieties BG12-1, BG367-3, BG379-2, and Thai variety BKNBR1030-51-1-1-2-1 were also resistant (see table). All other varieties were susceptible or highly susceptible. □

Resistance of rice varieties to leaffolder, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Score ^a	Variety	Origin
1	GEB24, PTB33	India
3	BG12-1, BG367-3, BG379-2	Sri Lanka
	BKNBR1030-51-1-1-2-1	Thailand
	IR21937-26-2-3	IRRI
	TKM6	India
5	BR220-1-1	Bangladesh
	Chianung 51-P1-66-1020	Taiwan, China
	IR21929-12-3-3,)	
	IR21931-47-3-3,)	IRRI
	IR9209-26-2-2-2-3)	
	Kannagi, T2005	India
7	IR13429-170-3,)	
	IR19575-65-2-2-3)	IRRI
	Kaohsiung Senyw 204	Taiwan, China
	OR100-25, OR55-9,)	
	TNAU9039-14,)	
	TNAU9227-1,)	India
	UPR311-19-2-1,)	
	UPR82-1-7, W1263)	
9	NR59, RNR67580	India
	Surya medal (12923)	Indonesia
	X2-0-1., 343-0.1.	Vietnam
	TN1	Taiwan, China

^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Deep water

Screening rice varieties for deepwater tolerance

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More than 12,000 ha of rice lands in Tamil Nadu are submerged or flooded for up to 4 months, Sep-Jan, during the vegetative phase. Local varieties TNR1 and TNR2 yield from 0.8 to 1.0 t/ha.

Twenty-four varieties from the Tamil Nadu Agricultural University germplasm collection were screened at IRRI for various characters that contribute to deepwater tolerance: submergence toler-

ance, salt tolerance, elongation ability, nodal rooting, and kneeing ability.

Submergence tolerance. Ten-day-old seedlings planted in trays were submerged (30 cm) in a water tank along with the check varieties FR13A (resistant) and IR42 (susceptible). Water temperature was maintained at 30°C and light intensity at 400 lux at the tray level. Trays were removed after 7 days and plants were scored 5 days after removal.

Submergence tolerance scores indicated that only TNR1, Dhanya, and Birpak had some degree of tolerance. Submergence tolerance, therefore, does not seem to be a crucial limiting factor for varietal development in deepwater.

Salt tolerance. Seedlings were grown in normal culture solution and transplant-

ed to saline soil with E. C. 9 mS/cm. Subsequent irrigation was with normal water. Cultivars were scored for salinity tolerance 4 weeks after transplanting (see table). TNR1, Ponkambi samba, Kattuvanam, Kar paddy, Dulai Baron, Kala or Black Aman, and Ponni showed tolerance equal to that of the check variety Pokkali.

Elongation ability. Four-week-old seedlings raised in small plastic pots were submerged in 40-cm water. Water level was increased to 90 cm at a rate of 10 cm/day and maintained for 1 week. Plants were removed and height, number of elongated internodes, and nodal rooting were recorded (see table). Elongation varied from 17 to 65 cm (25 to 129% increase). TNR1 and Ponkambi samba had maximum elongation ability. Chingair and Birpak had more

Rice varieties tested for various deepwater traits.

Variety	Submergence tolerance score ^a	Salt tolerance score ^a	Elongation ability			Elongated internodes (no.)	Kneeing ability
			Final height (cm)	Elongated height (cm) ^b	% of elongation		
TNRI	5	3	119	64	114	2	1
Ponkambi samba	9	3	112	63	129	2	7
Kattuvanam	9	3	111	47	73	2	3
Sarapalli samba	9	5	112	55	95	3	5
Sirumani Amon	9	9	115	56	95	2	3
Deepwater type	9	7	86	17	25	1	3
Donradao	9	7	117	50	75	1	3
Kar paddy	9	3	140	63	82	2	5
Dulai Aman	9	9	106	50	89	1	5
Dulai Baron	9	3	92	26	39	1	7
Dhanya	5	7	115	56	95	3	5
Akulu	9	5	118	52	75	3 ^c	3
Poongar	9	7	84	37	77	3	9
Kala or Black Aman	9	3	93	42	82	1	5
Chingair	9	5	133	65	96	3 ^c	5
Lalkanai	9	9	134	63	89	3	5
Birpak	7	9	140	63	82	4 ^c	1
Lakhi	9	9	110	46	72	3	3
Aeb 368 Rip P type	9	9	95	31	48	1	9
Perunel	9	7	102	39	62	3 ^c	7
White Ottadan	9	9	109	32	42	2	7
Gutak	9	7	77	27	52	2	9
Mahsuri	9	7	111	37	50	2	7
Ponni	9	3	71	30	73	1	7

^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice Scale. ^b Final height minus height before submergence. ^c Presence of nodal roots.

elongated internodes. Chingair, Birpak, Akulu, and Perunel had profuse nodal roots, which increase plant nutrient uptake.

Kneeing ability. Sixty-five-day-old plants were pulled out gently and placed horizontally on the puddled field. Water depth was maintained at 2 cm. Three days

later angle of kneeing was scored (see table). TNRI and Birpak had the most pronounced kneeing.

Photoperiod sensitivity. Seedlings were raised in plastic pots and subjected to photoperiod treatment for 10, 12, 14, and 16 hours. All the varieties treated with 10 and 12 hours photoperiod flow-

ered. Sarapalli samba, Aeb 368 Rip P, and Gutak flowered at the 14 hour treatment, and were considered photoperiod insensitive. (Aeb 368 Rip P did not flower at 16 hours.) All other varieties were photoperiod sensitive and had relatively long basic vegetative phase. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Hybrid rice

Inheritance of polycaryopsis and breeding of polycaryoptic male-sterile rice

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Polycaryoptic rices WX154 (Korea) and Double Rice (Bangladesh), which have more than two ovaries and four stigmas in each floret, were crossed with normal rice varieties 7101 and HR1619-6-2-1,

respectively, and with each other. The F₁ of the crosses of polycaryoptic and normal rices were normal. Segregation in the F₂s agreed with the ratio of three normal to one polycaryoptic. Results

indicate that polycaryopsis in WX154 and Double Rice is each controlled by a single recessive gene. The F₁ of the cross WX154/Double Rice was normal, and the F₂ segregated into nine normal to seven

Segregation for polycaryopsis in the F₂ of the crosses between polycaryoptic WX154^a and normal marker line 7101, polycaryoptic Double Rice^b and normal rice HR1619-6-2-1, and WX154 and Double Rice, IRRI.

Cross	F ₁	F ₂ plants (no.)			Ratio	x ²	P
		Normal	Poly-caryoptic	Total			
WX154/7101	Normal	232	68	300	3:1	0.871	.25-.50
HR1619-6-2-1/Double Rice	Normal	139	48	187	3:1	0.045	.50-.90
WX154/Double Rice	Normal	229	158	387	9:7	1.341	.10-.50

^a From Korea. ^b From Bangladesh.